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SHORT DISTANCE BETWEEN THE BOTTOMHOLE AND THE PERFORATION INTERVAL AS A HINDERING FACTOR FOR HYDRAULIC FRACTURING

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Abstract

The purpose of the paper is to determine the presence and degree of influence of the close location of the well bottomhole to the perforation interval during standard proppant fracturing in vertical and directional wells to clarify the recommended measures in accordance with the conditions of hydraulic fracturing. In the industrial practice of some companies, the classification of hindering factors, including the short distance between the bottomhole and the perforation interval, through which the fracturing mixture is injected, is assumed. The paper presents a method to measure, confirm or deny the influence of this factor on the risks of hydraulic fracturing. The scientific novelty of the work lies in the application of a new approach to risk assessment of the considered factors, including the definition of metrics and statistical analysis of the level of correlation between the measured parameters and the proposed metrics. As a result, the method was developed and the calculation on its basis, which shows the refutation of the impact of the factor under consideration. Recommendations were developed to consider this fact, including inexpediency of treatment volume limitation in given conditions that potentially increases hydraulic fracturing efficiency when current bottomhole is close to the treatment interval.

Keywords: proppant fracturing, fracturing risks, backfill, sump, perforation interval, fracture packing, technological complexities of fracturing, categorical analysis.

Short distance between the bottomhole and the perforation interval as a hindering factor for hydraulic fracturing

In industrial practice of hydraulic fracturing, as well as in a series of publications, there is a requirement to have a certain distance below the perforation interval, free for the movement of liquid or proppant mixture during the process [1]. This distance is often referred to as a sump, and in this publication the term sump will be taken as the distance from the bottom of the perforation interval to the current bottomhole during hydraulic fracturing, taking into account the planned backfill (Figure 1a). Service companies for hydraulic fracturing, as a rule, low value of the sump, and especially its absence, is accepted as a complicating factor [2]. Accordingly, in such cases, compensatory measures are suggested, including limitation of treatment volume, increase of fracturing fluid viscosity and pumping rate. Based on the sump data, limitations, which, in combination with other technical and geological conditions, reduce the potential effect of hydraulic fracturing, can be determined at the planning stage of hydraulic fracturing processes [3].

For many technical limitations of the fracturing process, their essence can be defined explicitly and no additional confirmation of the dependencies is required. For example, the influence of tubing diameter

on friction is noted in every well without exception and measured by direct method, which eliminates the need for confirmation. However, in some other cases, when the factor does not appear every time or cannot be measured directly, the influence of the factor passes into the category of risks appearing with a certain probability. In such cases, it is necessary to use statistics to confirm the risk in question. Also, in these cases, statistical analysis can be used to estimate the probability and consequences of the risk. The impact of a sump, as shown in detail below, belongs to this type of factor.

The hypothesis about the negative effect of a small sump is based on two assumptions. First, it is assumed that some proppant is settling at the bottom of the well during injection. Under this assumption, the small sump may decrease to 0 during injection, and then gradually settling proppant may partially or completely overlap the perforation interval, followed by an increase in frictional pressure loss in the perforations and process complications, respectively (Figure 1b). Second, the small sump value is associated with the risk of inaccurate determination of the current bottomhole depth and possible overlap of the perforations before work commences, with the risk of consequences similar to the first assumption. Figure 1 schematically illustrates the above processes.

Pic.1 Risk of proppant settlement during hydraulic fracturing.

An important remark to the settling assumption is the lack of experimental and theoretical data confirming the fact of the specified risk. Turbulent movement of the proppant-fluid mixture is expected to occur in the sump interval (Figure 1a), but proppant settling during this process (Figure 1b) has not been confirmed experimentally. Confirmation or rejection of this assumption is complicated by the lack of direct observation or recording of the process [4]. After stopping pumping, settlement of proppant residue does occur, as noted in laboratory tests, which limits the possibility of confirming with measurements of the current bottomhole after hydraulic fracturing. The second uncertainty is proppant settlement in the perforation interval during injection. For those cases where there is no sump during well preparation or presumed settlement has occurred during the process, it is unclear whether proppant settlement can continue while the mixture is moving from the production casing space into the perforations [5].

Statistics can be applied to confirm or reject the influence of the indicated factor. The conclusions presented on the basis of statistics cannot fully prove the validity of all details of the hypothesis, but statistically significant influence of the parameter can become the basis for further study of the detected phenomenon. Conversely, the lack of influence on explicit measurable metrics can be the basis for conclusions about the invalidity of such a hypothesis [6].

For statistical analysis, 620 non-horizontal wells with proppant fracturing were selected. The size of the sump was determined as a variable $Distance$ by equation 1:

$$Distance = \begin{cases} h_b - Perf_d, & \text{for } h_b - Perf_d > 0 \\ 0, & \text{for } h_b - Perf_d \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where h_b – depth of backfill or current face in the absence of backfill, $Perf_d$ – lower boundary of the perforation interval. Negative values of $h_b - Perf_d$ may be obtained for those cases where the perforation is partially overlapped by the backfill, in which case the sump should be assumed to be 0 [7].

For further categorical analysis, a categorical variable $Distance_{cat}$ was added, dividing the sump into 3 categories: «0-1 m», «1-2 m» and «More of 2m».

Two metrics have been selected to evaluate the effect of the variable. The first metric is $Propp_{needs}$, represents the mass of proppant left in the wellbore in excess of the planned underproduction. Thus, this metric would be 0 for a technologically successful process and >0 for a process complication, with the higher the complication, the higher the value of the metric. The average value of the metric is suitable for describing the technical complexity of a sample of fracturing processes.

The second metric, $ISIP_{growth}$, represents the increase in the actual ISIP of the fracture relative to the planned value. This metric allows to fix the non-predicted effect of fracture packing. An increase in the average value of the metric will indicate the presence of an additional fracture packing factor in the sample relative to the sample with a lower average value of this metric. Since a drop in the ISIP below the predicted value indicates a reduced or absent packing effect, or at least the absence of an additional, unaccounted for factor causing packing, to the same extent as a zero value, all negative values of the metric are equated to 0.

A general categorical analysis, as a first approximation, showed a decrease in the probability and volume of technological complication during hydraulic fracturing, as well as a decrease in the packing effect.

Table 1

First approximation of categorical analysis

Category	Average metric Propp_needs	Average metric ISIP_growth
0-1 m	0,086	31,8
1-2 m	0,064	28,6
More of 2m	0,072	27,8
Average of all	0,072	28,2

Nonlinearity of the decreasing trend of the metric *Proppneeds*, as well as the slight difference between the samples in the different categories indicated the possible presence of hidden dependencies. A search was conducted by adding subcategories.

Table 2

Extended categorical analysis

Category	Average metric Propp_needs	Average metric ISIP_growth
0-1 m		
Producing wells	0,086	31,8
1-2 m		
Just drilled	0,000	7,3
Producing wells	0,067	29,5
More of 2m		
Just drilled	0,109	32,8
Producing wells	0,069	27,3
Average of all	0,072	28,2

The extended categorical analysis includes a division within categories into subcategories of well type-operating or post-drilling fracturing. The extended categorical analysis showed a relatively greater influence of well status on metrics than the category by sump size, but relationships are apparent.

To clarify the presence of statistical relationships obtained, categorical analysis was conducted for the two most common processing objects in the sample under consideration.

Table 3

Categories by development object

Category	Average metric Propp_needs	Average metric ISIP_growth
D0	0,079	36,3
0-1 m	0,433	43,2
1-2 m	0,000	60,8
More of 2m	0,071	34,7
D1a	0,142	32,1
0-1 m	0,000	16,9
1-2 m	0,104	32,5
More of 2m	0,170	33,8
Average of all	0,104	34,6

A comparison across development objects showed an unexpected result. Previously revealed dependence, despite its weak manifestation, manifested itself for different data slices, but for formation D1a, contrary to the initial hypothesis, showed an opposite trend for both metrics. Such trends are possible only if two conditions are met simultaneously - low value of absolute difference of values and presence of distortions when converting a real variable into a categorical one. The resulting scatter is really not large - in the first approximation

it is a deviation of no more than 9 kg of proppant and 3.5 atm from the overall average value. Differences of this magnitude could have been caused by distortions in the conversion of the variables.

To visually assess the possible existence of a relationship between complicated fracture conditions and the sump value, below is a graph where the sorted *ISIP_{growth}* metric is compared with the sump values as a "point cloud".

Pic.2 Sumpf and ISIP metrics

The uniform density of sump points in Figure 2 visually demonstrates the lack of correlation between the measured parameter and the metric. Thus, the study of the data set showed that there does not seem to be a significant influence of sump size on the technological risks of hydraulic fracturing and this factor should not limit the use of proppant hydraulic fracturing technologies, including the volume of proppant used.

Conclusions and recommendations

1. Conducting a simplified statistical analysis similar to the presented analysis allows to exclude at the initial stage the hypotheses that potentially have no effect on the technologically significant parameters of hydraulic fracturing.

2. The result of the analysis does not exclude the possibility of proppant settlement on the well bottomhole, but shows the absence of significant influence of the sump on the risks during hydraulic fracturing, which may be due to stopping the proppant settlement process when the sump is filled with proppant.

3. Based on the fact that there are no additional complications, it is recommended to exclude the factor of close location of perforation interval to the bottomhole from the risk factors when performing standard proppant fracturing.

4. The analysis identified potentially higher risk categories, including post-drilling fracturing and D1a layered fracturing - it is recommended to conduct additional data review, including for confirmation of these hypotheses with the help of statistics.

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